

Research Writing Workshop at Simara College

One-Day Research Writing Workshop

With

Dr. Anjay Kumar Mishra
Nepal's Leading Management Scientist

Discussions on common challenges and best practices in research writing. Tips for crafting compelling introductions, structuring arguments, and presenting findings. Guidance on selecting appropriate journals and navigating the publication process. Opportunities for peer feedback and networking with fellow researchers.

Organized by :Simara College, Simara bara

Venue: Simara College, Simara, Bara

Date: 2081/03/15

Organized by: Research Management Cell , Simara College, Simara, Bara

Prepared By: Ms Soni Karki

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29 June 2024

A Brief Report

Moderator: Mr. Salikram Adhikari, Campus Chief

Convener: Ms Soni Karki

Co-conveners:

Sangita Khanal

Yadav Thapa

Krishna Gautam

Facilitator: Dr. Anjay Kumar Mishra, Management Scientist

Overview

Simara College recently hosted a highly successful One-Day Research Writing Workshop, facilitated by Dr. Anjay Kumar Mishra, a prominent figure in the field of management science in Nepal. The workshop, held on 2081/03/15, aimed to enhance the research writing skills of participants, offering them valuable insights and practical guidance.

Objectives of the One-Day Research Writing Workshop at Simara College

- To Enhance the participants' ability to write clear, coherent, and compelling research papers.
- To identify and provide solutions to common challenges faced in research writing, such as formulating research questions and conducting literature reviews.
- To disseminate best practices in research writing, including tips for crafting introductions, structuring arguments, and presenting findings.
- To offer guidance on selecting appropriate journals for publication and navigating the publication process effectively.
- To create opportunities for participants to receive constructive feedback on their work from peers and to provide feedback to others.

- To facilitate networking among researchers to build connections, share knowledge, and foster a collaborative research community.
- To utilize the extensive experience and expertise of Dr. Anjay Kumar Mishra to provide authoritative insights and practical advice on research writing and publishing.

Workshop Highlights

1. Interactive Sessions:

Dr. Anjay Kumar Mishra led a series of engaging and interactive sessions, drawing from his extensive experience in research and publishing. These sessions provided a platform for participants to learn, discuss, and practice various aspects of research writing.

2. Common Challenges and Best Practices:

The workshop addressed common challenges faced by researchers, such as formulating research questions, conducting literature reviews, and maintaining academic integrity. Dr. Mishra shared best practices to overcome these challenges, emphasizing the importance of clarity, coherence, and critical thinking in research writing.

3. Crafting Compelling Introductions

Participants learned how to craft compelling introductions that capture the reader's attention and clearly present the research problem. Dr. Mishra highlighted the elements of a strong introduction, including background information, research gaps, and the study's significance.

4. Structuring Arguments and Presenting Findings:

The workshop provided practical tips on structuring arguments logically and presenting research findings effectively. Dr. Mishra discussed various methods for organizing content, using evidence to support claims, and ensuring the research narrative flows seamlessly.

5. Selecting Appropriate Journals:

Guidance was provided on selecting appropriate journals for publication, taking into consideration factors such as journal scope, impact factor, and audience. Dr. Mishra also shared strategies for navigating the publication process, including manuscript preparation, submission guidelines, and responding to reviewers' comments.

6. Peer Feedback and Networking:

The workshop offered opportunities for peer feedback and networking, allowing participants to share their work, receive constructive critiques, and build connections with fellow researchers. This collaborative environment fostered a sense of community and mutual support among participants.

He shared for academicians, researchers, a collection of few Open Access Journals

<https://www.scienceopen.com/>

2. JSTOR

<https://about.jstor.org/oa-and-free/>

3. (OAL)OPEN ACCESS LIBRARY

<http://www.oalib.com/>

4. OXFORD ACADEMIC

https://academic.oup.com/journals/pages/open_access

5. KARGER

<https://www.karger.com/OpenAccess>

6. THIEME OPEN

<https://open.thieme.com/web/19/home>

7. OMNICS OPEN ACCESS

<https://www.omicsonline.org/>

8. BMC

<https://www.biomedcentral.com/>

9. MDPI

<https://www.mdpi.com/about/journals>

10. COGENT OA

<https://www.cogentoa.com/>

11. OPEN ACCESS

<https://www.omicsonline.org/>

12. ERUDIT

<https://www.erudit.org/en/>

13 HIGHWIRE

<https://www.highwirepress.com/>

14. DIRECTORY OF OPEN SCIENCE ARTICLES

<https://www.doaj.org/>

He further shared his editorial and asked these are also peer review open access journals for reading.

Mishra AK. How do you assess the Dynamics of Sustainable Business Operations during the COVID-19 Pandemic? J Adv Res HR Organ Mgmt 2021; 8(1&2): 23-24. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.24321/2454.3268.202103>

[2] Mishra AK. Geo Science & Remote Sensing in Effective Application. J Adv Res Geo Sci Rem Sens 2019; 6(3&4): 1-2 <https://doi.org/10.24321/2455.3190.201902>

- [3] Mishra AK. Effectiveness of Organization through Effective Human Resource Planning and Leading. J Adv Res HR Organ Mgmt 2019; 6(3&4): 1-2. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.24321/2454.3268.201902>
- [4] Mishra AK. What is the Best Journal to Publish your Scholarly Article? JAdvResConstUrbanArch 2021; 6(4): 31-33.
- [5] Mishra A.K, (2023). Welcome to the Ocean of Research across Technical Disciplines, JUEM 1(1), 1-6. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8116988>
- [6] Mishra, A. K. (2023). Together We Build Human Capital. Apex Journal of Business and Management (AJBM). 1(1), 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8402501>
- [7] Mishra, A. K. (2023). Welcome to KCM Project based Research in Business and Economics. New Perspective: Journal of Business and Economics, 6(1), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.3126/npjbe.v6i1.58867>
- [8] Mishra, A. K., (2023). Access to Scientific Publication through GS Spark. GSSpark: Journal of Applied Academic Discourse. 1(1), 1-6. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8381871>
- [9] Mishra, A. K. (2023). Welcome to an Action Against Mental Colonialism. Intellectual Journal of Academic Research (IJAR). 1(1), 1-6. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8273123>
- [10] Mishra, A.K. (2023). Wisdom of Worthy for Madhesh Province. GSWoW: Wisdom of Worthy Research Journal. 1(1), 1-6. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10441517>
- [11] Mishra, A. K. (2023). Anatomy of Brain Drain: A Painful Reality. International Research Journal of Parroha Multiple Campus (IRJPMC) 2(1), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10251093>
- [12] Mishra, A. K. (2024). Actions of Academic Institutions for Optimization of Human Capital. Apex Journal of Business and Management (AJBM). 2(1), 1 - 8 . <https://doi.org/10.61274/apxc.2024.v02i01.001>
- [13] Mishra, A. K. (2024). Government Investment in Agriculture and Policy Recommendations. SP Swag: SudurPashchim Wisdom of Academic Gentry Journal, 1(1), 1-10.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11056826>

Our campus chief instructed to print it and post in library and make students a habit of using it.

He also gave working sheet as Research Writing Exercise [follow link to learn] <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11121891> which is really excellent idea to teach research.

Conclusion

The One-Day Research Writing Workshop at Simara College, facilitated by Dr. Anjay Kumar Mishra, was a resounding success. Participants left with enhanced research writing skills, practical tips for improving their manuscripts, and a deeper understanding of the publication process. The workshop not only provided valuable learning experiences but also promoted collaboration and networking among researchers, contributing to the overall academic growth of the participants.

Profile of Facilitator

Anjay Kumar Mishra (PhD, Post Doc)

Professor,

Kathmandu College of Management

Kathmandu, Nepal

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Dr. Anjay Kumar Mishra is Professor at Kathmandu College of Management. He is doctorate in Project Management from Kanpur University and has completed his post Doctorate Research on Safe Project Operation in Nepal. He has served as Associate Professor and Research Director at School of Engineering, Madan Bhandari Memorial Academy Nepal, Joint constituent College of Pokhara

University. He is also regular visiting faculty and Thesis Supervisor at various colleges such as United Technical College, (Bharatpur, Chitwan), Institute of Engineering, Lumbini Engineering and Management Science College, (Rupandehi). He is Editor in Chief of DV Publication and ADR Publication, India and member of editorial board of Different international Journals. He is editor in chief of 7 national journals. He has been providing Consulting services to many organization such as Nepal Government, Ministry of Education Science and Technology, DWSS, Beton Infra tech LLP, Pune, He is member of Different Scientific society such as World Research Council, International Council for Occupational Health, South Asia Institute of Science and Engineering(SAISE),Member of All India Management Association, Fellow members of SAS Society, Member of Operation Research Society of Nepal, Country Coordinator of International American Council for Research and Development (IACRD), Member of Management Association of Nepal (MAN) and Research Scholar Hub, Gujarat.

He has obtained 6 patents including earlier cancer dictation device, 23 copyrights published more than 218 peer review research articles, Presented in 15 international conferences and many national conference, published 21 Conference Proceedings, 14 editorials along with 9 edited and 9 reference books.

He is an accomplished expert in the field of Occupational Safety and Health (OSH), Project Management and Operations Management and ranked as best scientist in his subject in Nepal as per AD Scientific Index.

- 1 <https://scholar.google.com/citations?hl=en&user=70NJhYAAAAAJ>
2. <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Anjay-Mishra>
3. <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2803-4918>
- 4 <https://privhq.ssrn.com/submissions/MyPapers.cfm?partid=3255631>
5. https://globalpeacechallenge2020.org/peace_ambassadors/dr-anjay-kumar-mis

Profile of Moderator

Mr. Salikram Adhikari

College Chief,

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Simara College's campus chief Mr. Salik Adhikari is a highly accomplished individual with extensive experience in education and community leadership. Adhikari holds a Master's degree in Accounting Management from Tribhuvan University and has served as a faculty member in the field of Management for 14 years.

With a strong background in management and leadership, the campus chief has been serving as the head of Simara College for 6 years. Under his guidance, the college has been committed to providing quality higher education and supporting underprivileged students through scholarship opportunities. In addition to his academic achievements, the campus chief has played pivotal roles in various organizations:

Founder Chairman of Sangalo Saving and Credit Cooperative Society Ltd.

Founder Chairman of Simara Public English School

Secretary of Bara District Federation of Saving and Credit Cooperative

President of Simara Jaycees in 2021

Adhikari can be reached at saugathurt@gmail.com

